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Project Newsletter

Newsletter Nr. 1 - February 2024

Official Project Start

INAIR, Coordination and Support Action funded by the EU's **Horizon Europe** Programme, officially started on **1 January 2024**. Our goal: **contributing to bridging the AI skills gap in Retail**.

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Kick-off Meeting in Brussels

On January 11th, 2024, representatives of the consortium members convened in Brussels at the **Confederation of European Businesses** (BusinessEurope) headquarters for INAIR's kick-off meeting.

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Towards the Identification of AI Skills Needs and Gaps in Retail

The consortium started its research of the skills needs and gaps in the field of AI for micro, small and medium-sized retailers in Cyprus, Germany, Italy, Poland and Romania.

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OFFICIAL PROJECT START

BRIDGING THE AI SKILLS GAPS IN THE RETAIL INDUSTRY

INAIR officially started on the first of January 2024. The project, funded by the Horizon Europe Programme, is coordinated by the Italian SME Lascò and implemented in partnership with the Digital Economy Lab of the University of Warsaw, the Software Engineering Lab of the University of Cyprus, the non-profit organisation Team 4 Excellence, the Italian Chamber of Commerce for Germany (ITKAM) and the design studio BSD.

Over **32 months**, the consortium will pursue the following objectives:

- OBJECTIVES**
- **Identify AI skills needs and gaps** for MSMEs working in the Retail sector in Cyprus, Germany, Italy, Poland, and Romania by July 2024;
 - Devise, test and implement a **scalable hybrid AI skills development program** to re-/up-skill at least 150 owners and employees of MSMEs working in the retail sector by April 2026;
 - Develop, by April 2026, **teaching and training resources** to support continuing vocational education and training providers in integrating the project AI skills development solutions.

Four **main outputs** will be produced by the consortium.

1. RESEARCH

Research to identify **multi-level AI skills needs and gaps for MSMEs working in the Retail sector.** The research report will collect both the findings and conclusions of the transnational research work, and recommendations and guidelines for designing an AI Core curriculum for MSMEs in Retail. Particularly, through desk research and co-creation workshops with relevant industry experts, the consortium will analyse in the countries involved the gaps in two key areas, such as ESCO’s transversal, information and digital skills needed to adopt AI, and sector-specific technical skills needed to adopt AI.

2. AI CORE CURRICULUM

The Curriculum will cover the fundamentals of AI and its applications for greening retailers and supporting them in optimizing resources and processes. Co-created with educators and industry experts, the curriculum will address the **transversal, green, information, digital and technical skills** needed to adopt AI to make their companies, processes and products more sustainable, following ESCO's classification. The curriculum will cover a **map of relevant web-based AI tools meeting the requirements defined in The Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI** developed by the EC's High-Level Expert Group on AI. The curriculum will be built on the fractal educational model, and embed modular learning approaches. Proficiency in the different domains will be defined via an AI Skills Assessment Tool, aimed at objectively assessing the knowledge and skills linked to the domain defined in the AI skills needs and gaps analysis.

3. OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

Through the Open Educational Resources, the consortium will transform the content outlined in the Learning Blocks into interactive learning resources (e.g., learning modules, interactive tools and simulations, learning games, and quizzes). The OERs will be developed in ENG and each partner's language and validated with industry experts.

4. E-LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

The Environment will serve as a platform to deliver the Open Educational Resources developed in the project and provide tailored learning experiences on AI for owners and employees of MSMEs in Retail. The platform's User Interface will be designed by experts in cognitive ergonomics, to contribute to enabling technology acquisition, increasing learners' interaction with the online learning environment and content, and decreasing the cognitive fluency required to learn complex technologies like AI. Furthermore, a **Practical Guide for Facilitators** will be developed to support Continuing vocational education and training providers in integrating the project AI skills development solutions into their work.

LEARN MORE >>

external link to the project website: ai4retail.eu

KICK-OFF MEETING IN BRUSSELS

HIGHLIGHTS

On **January 11th, 2024**, representatives of the consortium members convened in Brussels at the **Confederation of European Businesses** (*BusinessEurope*) headquarters for INAIR's kick-off meeting.

The meeting in Brussels was not just a formal gathering but a **vibrant exchange of ideas, visions and aspirations**, setting the stage for the project's innovative developments to support retailers in adopting AI technology.

The meeting, also attended by INAIR's Project Adviser on behalf of the funding authority, the **European Health and Digital Executive Agency** (*HADEA*), represented an opportunity to discuss the project roadmap, work plan and next steps and learn more about the role of **HADEA, the executive agency in charge of managing European programs and initiatives on behalf of the European Commission** in diverse sectors, including health, digital, food safety, industry, and space.

The meeting underscored the importance of collaborative efforts in achieving the project's ambitious goals. It set the roadmap for the upcoming phases, focusing on researching AI skills needs and gaps for micro, small and medium-sized retailers.

TOWARDS THE IDENTIFICATION OF AI SKILLS NEEDS AND GAPS IN RETAIL

RESEARCH

The consortium started its research of the skills needs and gaps in the field of AI for micro, small and medium-sized retailers in Cyprus, Germany, Italy, Poland and Romania.

The research work, led by the **Digital Economy Lab of the University of Warsaw** includes **desk research** and **co-creation workshops** with relevant industry experts to analyse the gaps in two key areas:

- **Transversal, information and digital skills needed to adopt AI**, as defined in the *European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations* (ESCO) classification and, therefore, the knowledge, attitudes and skills needed to critically analyse, interpret and rework information deriving from AI-driven solutions, and to creatively use AI to create knowledge, innovate processes and products and solve complex problems, including sustainability-related problems;
- **Sector-specific technical skills** needed to identify, evaluate, select and use AI-powered solutions to solve specific needs.

The research report will be published in **July 2024**.

Are you an employee, employer or an expert in the Retail industry?

If you are a retailer, worker or an expert in the industry, we encourage you to **share your experience with us** and contribute to the research.

Contact Us

external link to the project website

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